

Research

Comparison of Postoperative Analgesic Efficacy and Side Effects of Morphine with Fentanyl Added to Intrathecal Bupivacaine in Cesarean Section

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Abstract:Objective: Spinal anesthesia is a commonly used practice during cesarean sections due to its simplicity and ease of administration. Supplementing opioid drugs as adjuncts to spinal anesthesia can enhance the quality of sensory blockade and lead to improved postoperative analgesia. Morphine and fentanyl are commonly used opioids for this purpose. The objective of this study is to compare the postoperative analgesic efficacy and adverse effects of morphine and fentanyl when administered as supplements to intrathecal bupivacaine in cesarean section.

Methods: This is a prospective, randomized, single-blinded study. Sixty parturients were selected and randomly divided into two groups: Group M and Group F, with 30 parturients in each group. Group M received 1.8ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine with 0.1mg of preservative-free morphine (diluted in 0.4ml of normal saline), while Group F received 1.8ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine with 20µg of fentanyl. Both groups received a total of 2.2ml of local anesthetic solution for each patient. In each group, the patients received 1gm of intravenous paracetamol infusion every 6 hours. The time from the induction of spinal anesthesia to the first dose of rescue analgesia, as well as the total consumption of rescue analgesia (i.e., morphine) within 24 hours, were recorded. Opioid-related side effects were also recorded postoperatively.

Result: A total of 60 patients were selected for the study, with 30 patients in each group. The demographic data indicates no significant differences between the two groups. The duration from induction to the administration of the first rescue analgesia dose was significantly longer in group M (252.23±23.46 minutes) compared to group F (176.16±4.74 minutes) (p<0.0001). Moreover, the total consumption of rescue analgesia (morphine) over a 24-hour period was significantly lower in group M (7.6±0.77 mg) compared to group F (9.44±1.15 mg) (p<0.001). Additionally, the incidence of nausea/vomiting that required treatment was significantly higher in group M compared to group F (p<0.008).

Conclusion: The inclusion of intrathecal morphine in combination with hyperbaric bupivacaine results in an extended duration of analgesia post-cesarean section, when compared to fentanyl. Additionally, the morphine group requires less rescue analgesia (specifically, morphine) in comparison to the fentanyl group

Keywords: Spinal anesthesia, intrathecal morphine, intrathecal fentanyl, cesarean section postoperative analgesia.

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Introduction

Regional anesthesia is the most commonly used anesthetic technique for cesarean section due to its simplicity, efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and rapid onset of anesthesia. It provides adequate analgesia and muscle relaxation for the surgery, as supported by various studies [1,2,3,4].

The addition of opioids intrathecally as an adjunct to the spinal solution enhances analgesia, reduces the dosage of local anesthetic drugs, and provides satisfactory anesthesia during and after the cesarean section [5].

Effective pain relief following a caesarean section is crucial for promoting early ambulation, enabling the mother to feed her baby, and facilitating patient discharge. The inclusion of opioids as an adjunct to local anesthetic drugs improves the quality of sensory blockade and provides better postoperative analgesia. Morphine and fentanyl are commonly used opioids for this purpose [6].

Fentanyl, a phenyl piperidine derivative and synthetic opioid agonist, is more potent, lipid-soluble, and has a faster onset of action, but a relatively shorter duration of action. On the other hand, morphine, a hydrophilic phenanthrene derivative, has a slower onset of action and significantly longer duration of action compared to lipophilic opioids [7].

Our hypothesis is that the requirement of rescue analgesia postoperatively may be lower when morphine is added intrathecally as compared to fentanyl. The primary objective of this study is to compare the postoperative efficacy and duration of analgesia of adding morphine intrathecally with fentanyl in cesarean section. The secondary objective is to compare the side effects related to opioids, such as pruritus, nausea, vomiting, and respiratory depression.

Research Methodology

Sixty parturients aged 18 to 35 years, classified as ASA grade II, who were scheduled for elective cesarean section under spinal anesthesia at gestation of more than 37 weeks, were included in this prospective, randomized, single-blinded study. This study was approved by the Ethical Committee of Madhesh Institute of Health Sciences, Janakpur, Nepal. All patients were provided with written informed consent to participate in this trial. A detailed explanation of the aims and methods of the study was provided during the preoperative visit. Parturients were excluded from the study if they had contraindications to spinal anesthesia or analgesia, complicated pregnancies (e.g., severe preeclampsia, eclampsia, HELLP syndrome, or multiple pregnancies), neuromuscular disorders, chronic drug abuse, or a body mass index exceeding 35 kg/m². The patients were randomly divided into two groups, with randomization achieved through the use of sealed envelopes assigning them to either GroupM or GroupF.

Patients in GroupM received 1.8 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine with 0.1 mg of preservative-free morphine (diluted in 0.4 ml of normal saline), while patients in GroupF received 1.8 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine with 20 µg of fentanyl. Both groups received a total of 2.2 ml of local anesthetic solution per patient. Each patient fasted for at least six hours prior to the procedure. Upon arrival at the operating theater, the patient received 50 mg of ranitidine and 10 mg of metoclopramide intravenously for aspiration prophylaxis. Standard monitoring (noninvasive blood pressure, pulse oximetry, and electrocardiography) was applied. All patients were preloaded with 500 ml of lactate ringer solution over a 15-minute period prior to spinal anesthesia.

Spinal anesthesia was performed under aseptic precautions, with the patient in a sitting position, using a 25 G Quincke spinal needle introduced at the L3-L4 intervertebral space. After the observation of clear cerebrospinal fluid, the drug mixture was administered over a period of 10-15 seconds with a cephalad orientation of the spinal needle. Following spinal anesthesia, the patient was placed in a supine position with a 15° left uterine displacement, and the level of sensory block was assessed with a spirit swab. Surgery was only permitted after achieving a satisfactory blockade up to the level of T₆. Oxygen at a flow rate of 6 L/min was administered via a face mask to the patients. Blood pressure was monitored at 1-minute interval until stable, and then continued every 3 minutes. Hypotension was defined as a 20% reduction from the baseline systolic blood pressure. If this occurred, the patient was treated with a rapid infusion of 100 ml of lactate ringer solution and intravenous boluses of 6 mg of ephedrine or 50 mcg of

phenylephrine. After surgery, the patient was transferred to the recovery room for monitoring. The standard pain control protocol included 1gm paracetamol administered via intravenous infusion every 6 hours. The first dose was given 2 hours after the induction of spinal anesthesia. Additionally, intravenous morphine was provided as a rescue analgesia. The morphine was diluted to a concentration of 1mg/ml, and a 1ml bolus dose was administered as needed to relieve pain. After 30 minutes of monitoring vital signs in the recovery room, if the patient was stable, they were transferred to the postoperative obstetric ward. Vital signs, including heart rate, noninvasive arterial blood pressure, respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation, were monitored in the ward. Patients were instructed to use the bolus dose of rescue analgesia as needed. Careful assessment for side effects of opioid therapy was conducted.

During the postoperative period, the time from the induction of spinal anesthesia to the first use of rescue analgesia (intravenous morphine) and the total consumption of rescue analgesia (morphine) within 24 hours were recorded. Pain intensity was assessed based on movement, such as deep breathing or coughing, and bolus doses of rescue analgesia were administered according to the patient's demand until the pain was relieved. Trained staff nurses, who were blinded to the procedure, recorded the data. Vital signs were monitored hourly.

Side effects related to opioid usage, including pruritus, nausea and vomiting, sedation, urinary retention, and respiratory depression, were also recorded during the postoperative period. Respiratory depression was defined as a respiratory rate of less than 8 breaths per minute or arterial oxygen saturation below 90%.

Sample size for this study was estimated by considering the primary outcome as the mean time from induction to the first dose of rescue analgesia within a 24-hour period. We utilized an online sample size calculator for non-inferiority testing (<http://powerandsamplesize.com/Calculators/Compare-2-Means/2-Sample-Non-Inferiority-or-Superiority>). To detect a difference of one standard deviation (SD) between groups for this study outcome, it was determined that a sample size of 28 patients per group was required to achieve 80% power, with a one-sided significance level of $\alpha = 0.025$. To account for an anticipated dropout rate of 10%, the target enrollment was increased to 30 patients per group. Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 23. Mean, standard deviation, and proportions were calculated. Data were compared using independent t-tests or Chi-square tests as appropriate. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 60 patients were selected for the study. Thirty patients were allocated to Group M, and the other thirty patients were allocated to Group F. The demographic data are presented in Table 1. No significant differences were observed between the two groups in terms of age, weight, height, or period of gestation.

The time from induction to the first dose of rescue analgesia was significantly longer in Group M (252.23±23.46 minutes) as compared to Group F (176.16±4.74 minutes) ($p < 0.0001$) (Table 1) (Figure 1).

Table1: Shows baseline patients characteristic, Time from induction to first dose of analgesia and total consumption of rescue analgesia within 24hours.

Characteristics	GroupM (n-30)	GroupF (n-30)	p-value
	[mean ± SD]	[mean ± SD]	
Age (years)	24.67±3.51	24.27±3.05	0.640
Height (cm)	151.60±3.84	152.60±2.20	0.222
Weight (kg)	65.40±2.06	65.60±2.92	0.760
Period of gestation (week)	38.32±0.71	38.17±0.77	0.435
Time from induction to first analgesia (min)	252.23±23.46	176.16±4.74	<0.0001
consumption of rescue	7.6±0.77	9.44±1.15	<0.001

analgesia(morphine) in 24 hours(mg)			
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Data are presented as mean±SD, p<0.05 shows significant.

Figure-1: Mean time to first analgesia [min] by Group

The total consumption of rescue analgesia (morphine) over a 24-hour period was significantly lower in Group M (7.6 ± 0.77 mg) as compared to Group F (9.44 ± 1.15 mg) ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1) (Figure 2).

The incidence of nausea/vomiting requiring treatment was significantly higher in Group M as compared to Group F ($p < 0.008$) (Table 2). However, there was no significant difference in the incidence of pruritus between the two groups, and both groups required no treatment for it. None of the patients in either group experienced respiratory depression.

Table 2: Shows Nausea/vomiting and pruritus status among the patients.

Characteristics	Morphine Group (n-30)	Fentanyl Group (n-30)	p-value
Nausea/vomiting			
Presence	23	13	0.008
Absence	7	3	
Pruritus			
Presence	22	16	0.108
Absence	8	14	

Data are presented as mean±SD, p<0.05

Discussion

In this study, it was found that the consumption of morphine (bolus) for postoperative analgesia was lower when intrathecal morphine was used during induction as compared to intrathecal fentanyl. The time from induction to the first demand of morphine was longer in the intrathecal morphine group than the intrathecal fentanyl group. Similar results were documented by Sibilla et al. and G Siti salmah et al. in their studies [1, 8].

The duration and effectiveness of analgesia have been shown to be dose-dependent, although a ceiling effect is observed with intrathecal doses of morphine above 0.1mg [9]. However, the incidence of side effects increases with higher doses and may limit the amount of morphine that can be administered. Less than 1% of patients developed respiratory depression at or above 0.2mg intrathecal morphine, and this effect can be delayed for 12-24 hours [9,10]. The delayed effect is due to the slow transfer of hydrophilic morphine through cerebrospinal fluid circulation to the fourth ventricle, where it acts on opioid receptors adjacent to the respiratory center [8]. None of the patients in this study experienced any clinically detectable sedation or respiratory depression when using a low dose of morphine (0.1mg) intrathecally. This may be due to the small sample size and may correlate with the further study.

In this study, the incidence of nausea/vomiting was significantly higher in the morphine group as compared to the fentanyl group, requiring treatment with intravenous metoclopramide. Vomiting may be due to either the cephalic spread of the drug in the cerebrospinal fluid to the chemoreceptor trigger zone (CTZ), or the vascular uptake and transfer to the vomiting center and CTZ. Nausea and vomiting are common side effects that can be easily treated with antiemetics such as metoclopramide, antihistamines, and ondansetron [10,11,12,13,14].

There was no significant difference in the incidence of pruritus in both groups, which did not require treatment with intravenous chlorpheniramine. Intrathecal opioids commonly cause pruritus, which is usually localized to the face and neck areas. In obstetric patients, pruritus may be due to the interaction of estrogen with opioid receptors. It typically occurs within a few hours of injection and may precede the onset of analgesia. Paradoxically, antihistamines may be effective, most likely as a secondary effect of their primary sedative effect. An opioid antagonist, naloxone 0.2mg, is effective in relieving opioid-induced pruritus [10,11,13,14].

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that the incorporation of intrathecal morphine alongside hyperbaric bupivacaine yields a satisfactory and longer-lasting analgesic effect following cesarean section, in comparison to intrathecal fentanyl. Consequently, the morphine group exhibited reduced consumption of rescue analgesia as compared to the fentanyl group.

The effectiveness of rescue analgesia was tested by administering a bolus dose of morphine instead of using PCA pump.

Although the VAS score was not documented, the level of pain intensity was evaluated based on the patient's movements (such as breathing or coughing).

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